

α -Oximino- β -semicarbazones of Benzoylacetarylamides and Their Cyclisation to *vicinal*-Triazoles

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Seven α -oximino- β -semicarbazones of benzoylacetarylamides have been prepared by condensing semicarbazide and α -oximinobenzoylacetarylamides. α -Oximino- β -semicarbazones of benzoylacetarylamides were cyclised in thionyl chloride or acetic anhydride/sodium acetate to give 2-carbamido-5-carboxyarylamino-4-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles. The compounds synthesised were characterised by elemental analysis, uv and ir spectra.

OXIMINOHYDRAZONES have been shown to possess biological activity^{1,2} by virtue of the presence of the $-\text{CONH}-\text{N}=\text{C}-$ group and the $=\text{NOH}$ group, which impart antiparasitic, fungicidal, and bactericidal properties to such compounds. Patel and Mankad³⁻⁵ have shown that α -oximino- β -hydrazones of acetoacetarylamides can be utilised as chelating agents for the quantitative estimation of transition metal ions, such as Ni and Pd, either alone or in presence of other metals. Cyclisation of oximinohydrazones afforded *vicinal*-triazoles whose mechanism of formation has been proposed by Ruppert and Nilsson⁶. Several investigators⁷⁻¹¹ have synthesised *vic*-triazoles from oxime hydrazones and shown to possess whitening property and pharmacological activity.

In view of the above, it was considered worthwhile to undertake a systematic study of the preparation and characterisation of α -oximino- β -semicarbazones of benzoylacetarylamides and their cyclised products, *vic*-triazoles.

Experimental

Melting points of all the compounds are uncorrected. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen are

estimated using C.H.N. Coleman instrument. Uv spectra were recorded on a Beckman 36 spectrophotometer in ethanol. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Carl Zeiss UR-10 spectrophotometer.

α -Oximino- β -semicarbazones were prepared by the method of Knorr¹² and crystallised from aqueous ethanol.

α -Oximino- β -semicarbazones of benzoylacetarylamides (1): Condensation of the α -oximino- β -semicarbazones of benzoylacetarylamides with semicarbazide hydrochloride was carried out by taking α -oximino- β -semicarbazones of benzoylacetarylamides in ethanol and aqueous solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride in an equimolecular proportions and a few drops of concentrated HCl. On keeping for 2-3 h, the product separated was filtered and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. In all the cases the yield obtained was within the range of 75 to 80%. The characteristics and analytic data are recorded in Table 1.

2-Carbamido-5-carboxyarylamino-4-phenyl-1,2,3-triazoles (2): α -Oximino- β -semicarbazone of benzoylacetarylamide (0.5 g) were mixed with excess of freshly distilled thionyl chloride (about 20 ml). The contents were refluxed at 80-90° for 3 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off at atmospheric

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS, ANALYTICAL AND UV SPECTRAL DATA OF α -OXIMINO- β -SEMICARBAZONES OF BENZOYLACETARYLAMIDES (1)

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C(d)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			λ_{max} nm	log ϵ
				C	H	N		
1.	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	167	58.64 (59.07)	4.85 (4.62)	19.06 (21.45)	277 248	3.5 3.6
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	148	59.89 (60.17)	5.78 (5.02)	20.66 (20.65)	267	4.1
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	130	60.80 (60.17)	5.30 (5.02)	21.46 (20.65)	277 249	3.6
4.	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	161	52.13 (53.40)	4.36 (3.89)	18.48 (19.47)	266	4.1
5.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	118	53.71 (53.40)	3.94 (3.89)	21.58 (19.47)	260	3.5
6.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	146	56.96 (57.46)	4.97 (4.79)	18.21 (19.72)	261	4.2
7.	<i>m</i> -(OH) ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	142	62.41 (61.19)	5.54 (5.38)	20.85 (19.83)	280 246	4.2 4.1

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND UV SPECTRAL DATA OF *vic*-TRIAZOLES (2)

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C(d)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	log ϵ
				C	H	N		
1.	H	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	125	63.16 (62.54)	4.98 (4.23)	21.50 (22.80)	275	4.3
2.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	148	64.76 (63.55)	4.64 (4.67)	22.03 (21.80)	260	4.5
3.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	182	64.30 (63.55)	4.54 (4.67)	20.69 (21.80)	275	4.3
4.	<i>o</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	123	57.95 (56.22)	3.56 (3.51)	20.71 (20.49)	262	4.4
5.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	138	57.49 (56.32)	3.61 (3.51)	20.16 (20.49)	270	4.2
6.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	120	59.77 (60.53)	4.33 (4.45)	20.2 (20.77)	265	4.3
7.	<i>m</i> -(OH) ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃	103	63.98 (64.47)	5.15 (5.07)	20.54 (20.89)	275	4.4

pressure while the traces was removed by distillation *in vacuo* after adding benzene and petroleum ether successively. The semisolid residue was then removed in the solid form by adding diethylether. Ether was allowed to evaporate and the fine solid powder obtained was dried at 50-60° and then kept in vacuum desiccator till the odour of thionyl chloride disappeared. The compounds thus obtained were recrystallised from ethanol and are listed in Table 2.

The 2,4,5-trisubstituted-1,2,3-triazoles prepared by the above method were also synthesised by the action of acetic anhydride (~20 ml)/sodium acetate (~0.2 g) on the corresponding α -oximino-semicarbazones (0.1-0.2 g) at reflux temperature for 3 h, followed by the distillation of excess acetic anhydride and pouring the residual mass over ice. The solid product separated in each case was crystallised from ethanol. The melting points of the products were found to be the same as those prepared by the first method.

Results and Discussion

α -Oximino- β -semicarbazones of benzoylacetyl-amides (1) have been assigned *anti*-configuration¹³.

Table 1 shows the uv data for oximosemicarbazones. In 1, the new chromophoric system N=C-C(=N)-C=O has exhibited a band¹³ at $\lambda_{\max}$ 260-280 nm (log ϵ 3.5-4.2) and the second band which is observed in some cases is found at 246-249 nm (log ϵ 3.6-4.1.) The position is nearly the same as observed in the parent compounds, benzoylacetyl-amides (245 nm). The ir spectra of 1 have exhibited bands at 3100-3400 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to free NH₂ of carbazide moiety and bonded NH of amide and OH of oxime stretching¹⁴. The bands at 1600-1640 and 960-970 cm⁻¹ are assigned to C=N and N-O stretchings, respectively¹⁴. The secondary amide bands¹⁵ are located at 1660-1675, 1535-1590 and around 1300 cm⁻¹. The 2,4,5-trisubstituted-*vic*-triazoles prepared here do not show tendency to form metal complexes with transition metal ions which indicates the absence of free =NOH and the formation of triazole ring.

The mechanism of the *vic*-triazole (2) formation from 1 in the presence of thionyl chloride has been proposed as in Scheme 1.

where, R = H, *o*-CH₃, *p*-CH₃, *o*-Cl, *p*-Cl, *o*-OCH₃, *m*-(OH)₂

Scheme 1

It is suggested that under reaction condition the compounds undergo first a stereochemical change from *anti* to *amphi* configuration (Scheme 2) and then follow the cyclodehydration.

Scheme 2

TABLE 3—IR SPECTRAL DATA (ν cm^{-1}) OF α -OXIMINO- β -SEMICARBAZONES OF BENZOYLACETARYLAMIDES (1) AND *vic*-TRIAZOLES (2)

Sl. no.*	N-H or OH, primary amine	C=N	N-O	<i>vic</i> -Triazole ring	Ring breathing and C-H in-plane	sec.-Amides		
						I	II	III
1.	3160-3260 b	1600 s	960 ss	—	—	1670 s	1545 s	1298 s
1 ^a .	3220 m, 3440 m	1600 s	—	1245 m, 1190 s, 1160 s	1100 s, 1040 s, 1020 m, 920 s	1675 s	1540 s	1300 s
2.	3125-3225 b, 3410 m	1640 s	960 ss	—	—	1675 s	1580 s	1310 s
2 ^a .	3320 m, 3450 m	1610 s	—	1245 s, 1180 s, 1160 m	1120 m, 1070 m, 1020 m, 930 s	1675 s	1550 s	1310 s
3.	3210-60 b	1600 s	965 ss	—	—	1675 s	1550 s	1345 s
3 ^a .	3310 m, 3445 m	1600 s	—	1250 s, 1220 m, 1180 s	1180 s, 1100 s, 1040 m, 990 m	1670 s	1545 s	1300 s
4.	3150-3210 b, 3295 m	1640 s	970 ss	—	—	1670 s	1590 s	1300 s
4 ^a .	3300 m, 3450 m	1610 s	—	1260 m, 1225 s, 1175 s	1125 s, 1080 s, 1030 m, 990 m	1650 s	1540 s	1300 s
5.	3245-70 b 3410 m	1605 s	970 ss	—	—	1675 s	1545 s	1320 s
5 ^a .	300 m, 3445 m	1610 s	—	1250 s, 1220 m, 1180 s	1125 m, 1030 m, 950 m, 890 s, 875 s	1660 s	1550 s	1310 s
6.	3150-90 b, 3410 m	1600 s	960 ss	—	—	1570 s	1540 s	1320 s
6 ^a .	3320 m, 3450 m	1600 s	—	1260 m, 1210 m, 1185 s	1185 m, 1030 s, 950 s, 885 s	1675 s	1540 s	1310 s
7.	3210 m	1600 s	960 ss	—	—	1660 s	1535 s	1310 s
7 ^a .	3082 m, 3440 m	1600 s	—	1250 s, 1230 m, 1180 s	1180 s, 1050 m, 940 s, 875 s	1650 s	1630 s	1300 s

* Represent α -oximinosemicarbazones (1) as in Table 1 and those with ^a are corresponding *vic*-triazoles.

The uv spectral data (Table 2) of 2,4,5-trisubstituted-1,2,3-triazoles shows one intense band in the region 260-275 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.2-4.5). This is attributed to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition and is attributed to 1,2,3-triazole ring^{15,16}. Table 3 shows the infrared spectral data of *vic*-triazoles. The most important feature of these spectra is the presence and location of the *vic*-triazole ring vibrations and ring breathing bands. The bands around 1180 and 1250 cm^{-1} are attributed to *vic*-triazole ring vibrations. The peaks around 1125, 1050, 1000 and 900 cm^{-1} are assigned to *vic*-triazole ring breathing and C-H in-plane deformations. These values are in good agreement with the reported¹⁷ values for *vic*-triazoles. The absence of $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ band in *vic*-triazoles indicates the formation of *vic*-triazole ring with the disappearance of OH of oximino group of oximinosemicarbazones during the cyclodehydration reaction. The bands around 3440 and 3300 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{NH} of free primary amide ($-\text{CO}-\text{NH}_2$) and free secondary amide and *trans* associated secondary amide, respectively¹⁸. The bands due to C=N and secondary amide (C=O) are located at their usual positions¹⁵.

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